

Causative Factors of Substance Abuse Among Adolescent Secondary School Students in Aba: Counselling Implications

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<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5109174>

Abstract

This study examined the causative factors of substance abuse among secondary school students in Aba, Abia State. Two research questions were answered, and two null hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance guided the study. The study adopted the descriptive survey design. A sample of 120 students was purposively drawn from four randomly selected secondary schools in Aba which were noted for prevalence of substance abuse. 70 males and 50 females participated in this study, 65 of them were from high socio-economic background, while 55 were from low socio-economic status background. Their age range is between 15-19 years and their mean age was 16.12 years. The Drug Habit Scale (DHS) which has a test-retest reliability of 0.73 and a construct validity of 0.70 was used for data collection. The t-test statistic was used to test the two hypotheses at .05 level of significance. The result indicated that male and female students take drugs for different reasons. The result also showed that high or low socioeconomic status is not a determining factor of substance abuse. Some counselling implications of these findings were discussed and, the study recommended among others that drug users should be rehabilitated after treatment so as to avoid relapse.

Key words: Causative factors, Substance abuse, Adolescent, Students, Counselling

Introduction

Addiction is a social disease that has physical and psychological complications. Determination of causes of drug addiction plays an important role in the health planning. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), Substance abuse refers to the harmful or hazardous use of psychoactive substances, including alcohol and illicit drugs. It is now a major Public Health challenge all over the world. Complications of substance abuse by young people are grave including: increased odds of engaging in risky sexual behaviour, personality disorders, sexual violence, criminal tendencies and drug dependence among others.

Substance use among adolescent secondary school students ranges from experimentation to severe substance use disorders. All substance use, even experimental use, puts adolescents at risk of short-term problems, such as accidents, fights, unwanted sexual activity, and overdose. Substance use

also interferes with adolescent brain development. Adolescents are vulnerable to the effects of substance use and are at increased risk of developing long-term consequences, such as mental health disorders, underachievement in school, a substance use disorder, and higher rates of addiction, if they regularly use alcohol, marijuana, nicotine, or other drugs during adolescence (Ajala, 2009).

Being an adolescent and raising adolescents are enormous challenges. For some adolescents, illicit substance use and abuse become part of the landscape of their adolescent years. Although most adolescents who use drugs do not progress to become drug abusers or drug addicts in adulthood, drug use in adolescence is a very risky proposition. Even small degrees of substance abuse (for example, alcohol, marijuana, and inhalants) can have negative consequences. Typically, school and relationships, notably family relationships, are among the life areas that are most influenced by drug use and abuse. One of the most telling signs of an adolescents increasing involvement with drugs is when drug use becomes part of his/her daily life. Preoccupation with drugs can crowd out previously important activities and the way the adolescent views their self may change in unrealistic and inaccurate directions.

Generally, drugs are abused for various reasons and various causative factors predispose adolescents to it. Adolescents who are left alone for long periods of time or those movement are not monitored by parents or caregivers may undoubtedly have greater opportunity for exposure to drugs. Most teens used drugs and alcohol when going to friends' homes, spending the night out or when attending parties. It was suggested that parents or guardians should be aware of their wards movements such as to ask them where they are going and contact information so they can be contacted when outside the home. Let them know that at any time, a parent could call or drive and pick them up. The situation in Nigeria is even getting worse because of the economic conditions. The financial constrains pose serious constraints on addressing certain issues which are required by both parents and students.

One of the reasons for adolescent's substance abuse is that some parents abuse drugs as indicated by Huba, Maddahian and Bentler (2009). In his study, Barnes (2013) pointed out that perceived adult drug use was one of the reasons why adolescents end up getting into drug abuse. This was supporting Huba and Bentler (2010) who had also indicated this in their study. Abdu-Raheem (2013) is also supportive of that perceived adult drug use led to drug or substance abuse.

Other reasons indicated by different scholars include peer use (Newcomb, Maddahian & Bentler, 2009), poor school grades (Newcomb, Abdu-Raheem, 2013; Noyes & Mills, 1984; Phillips, Lewis & Gossett, 2015), poor relationships between adolescents and parents (Newcomb, Maddahian & Bentler, 2009), low self-esteem, depression, and psychological distress (Aneshensel & Huba, 2014; Kaplan, 2008; Newcomb, Maddahian & Bentler, 2009; Okafor, Obi & Oguzie, 2018), unconventionality and tolerance for deviance (Jessor & Jessor, 2012; Newcomb, Maddahian & Bentler, 2009).

Ajala (2009) opined that the problem of drug abuse is so grave that although it was originally conceived as the problem of selected few, it has extended beyond the characteristic of abusers. He went on to say that the abusers erroneously believed that drugs enhanced their performances, put them in a good mood; the accompanying problems of this act constitute a major threat to the well-being of the society. The spread of the cases of truancy, examination malpractices, lack of cultural values and other anti-social behaviours, have become a challenge to secondary schools administrators.

Adolescent substance abuse has been shown to be more common in males, however reports have shown increasing female participation in the vice as well as a trend towards multiple substance use (Egbonu, Ezechukwu, Chukwuka & Unakwe, 2004; Fatoye, 2003; Fatoye & Morakinyo, 2002;

Obot, 1993). Adolescents' who abuse substances are exposed to risks and consequences that can manifest physically, psychosocially and behaviorally (Goodman & Huang, 2002). The studies of Cotto and Weiss (2010) found that overall rate of substance use were significantly higher for males than females. A meta-analysis of marijuana and alcohol use by socio-economic status in adolescents Lemstra, Bennett and Neudorf (2008) found that the prevalence of marijuana and alcohol consumption was 22% higher in adolescents with a lower SES than in those with a higher SES. Trim and Chassin (2008) found that affluent neighbours may contribute to high level of substance use due to less supervision of children and more exposure to substance using peers.

From the studies thus reviewed on causative factors of substance abuse, it is evident that substance abuse is perhaps an attempt at adaptation. It means therefore that adolescents do drugs for the alteration of their state of consciousness in order to enhance good feelings and cope with pressures of life. The most frequently reported effect of all psychoactive substances is euphoria that is a state of wellbeing during which pre-existing problems seem to disappear, little wonder the appellation "mood modifying" for the psychoactive substances. But does it mean that alteration of consciousness is a right technique for adaptation in one's environment?

Objective of Study

The objective of this study therefore is to examine the factors that are responsible for the drug habit of secondary school students.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the causes of substance abuse among male and female secondary school students in Aba, Abia State?
2. What are causes of substance abuse among secondary school students based on their socio-economic status?

Null Hypotheses

Two null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- 1) There is no significance difference in the causes of substance abuse between male and female participants
- 2) There is no significance difference in the causes of substance abuse between high and low socio-economic status students

Method

The study adopted the descriptive survey design. A sample of 120 students was purposefully drawn from four randomly selected secondary schools in Aba Education zone in Abia State. There were 70 males and 50 females. 65 of the participants were from high socio-economic background while 55 were from low socio-economic background. Their age range between 15-19 years.

Instrument for Data Collection

The Drug Habit Scale (DHS), constructed by the researcher was used in collecting data for the study. It was specifically designed to collect information on the demographic background of the participants. It contains 30 items structured in a four point scale. The items were designed to assess the various factors that are causing drug abuse among the students. Being diagnostic in nature, it also helps the researcher in estimating drug habit of the participants, its prevalence and students attitude towards substance abuse. It has interval test- retest reliability co-efficient of 0.73. The interval was three weeks and 50

participants were used to establish the reliability of the instrument. The test also has a construct validity of 0.70.

Analysis of Data

The responses on the questionnaire were scored and analyzed using the t-test statistic. In the study, four variables were measured to access the causative factors of substance abuse among the students.

Results

To test the first null hypothesis which states that there will be no significant difference in the causes of substance abuse between male and female subjects, table 1 reveals the score mean of male and female participants which were compared using the t-test. The calculated t-value (3.29) is more than the table t-value of 1.96 which indicate a significant difference, hypothesis one is therefore rejected. The result indicate that the males and females have different reasons for abusing substances

Table 1: Comparison of Male and Female participants Causative Factors of Substance Abuse

Variable	N	X	SD	t-tab	t-cal.	P
Males	70	76.10	8.45	1.96	3.29	S*
Females	50	70.12	8.01			

*Significant

The second hypothesis which states that there will be no significant difference in the cause of substance abuse between high and low socio-economic status participants was also tested. In table 2, the mean score of the two groups were compared using t-test. The calculated t-value of 1.19 is less than the table t-value of 1.96, which indicate no significant different. The second Hypothesis is therefore retained. The result however indicates that the desire of the high socio-economic and low socio-economic status to get involved in substance abuse is equally strong.

Table 2: Comparison of Causative Factors of Substance Abuse between Participants with High and Low Socio-Economic Status

Variable	N	X	SD	t-tab	t-cal.	P
High Socio-Economic Status	65	72.02	8.01	1.96	1.19	NS*
Low Socio-Economic Status	55	72.08	8.40			

**Not Significant

Discussion

The findings of this study revealed that people get involved in substance abuse for various reasons in spite of its destructive nature and consequences. The findings of the first hypothesis showed that a significant relationship exists among the factors that influence drug habit in male and female participants. It is revealed in table 1 that out of 120 participant, 70 are males while 50 are females, which means that more males may be involved in substance abuse, more males scored higher than the females which is an indication of prevalence of substance abuse problem among males which their higher score seem to suggest, and more serious the problem. When the mean scores of both male and female were compared in Table 1, it shows that the scores of males were higher than that of females. The findings of this study agrees

with (Egbuonu, Ezechukwu, Chukwuka & Unakwe 2004; Fatoye, 2003; Fatoye & Morakinyo, 2002; Obot, 1993) who found that adolescent substance abuse has been shown to be more common in males, however reports have shown increasing female participation in the vice as well as a trend towards multiple substance use. The studies of Cotto and Weiss (2010) who found that overall rate of substance use were significantly higher for males than females, lend credence to the findings of this study.

The findings of the second hypothesis show that socioeconomic status is not a determining factor of substance abuse. The non-significant difference as revealed in the mean score of the two groups in Table 2 may be accounted for by the fact that children whether rich or poor will still have reasons for drug use. Some of these reasons as indicated by different scholars include peer use (Newcomb, Maddahian & Bentler, 2009), poor school grades (Phillips, Lewis & Gossett 2015; Noyes and Mills 1984; Newcomb, Abdu-Raheem, 2013), poor relationships between adolescents and parents (Newcomb, Maddahian & Bentler, 2009), low self-esteem, depression, and psychological distress (Aneshensel & Huba 2014; Kaplan 2008; Newcomb, Maddahian & Bentler, 2009; Okafor, Obi & Oguzie, 2018), unconventionality and tolerance for deviance (Jessor & Jessor, 2012; Newcomb, Maddahian & Bentler, 2009). However other studies like Lemstra, Bennett and Neudorf (2008) found that the prevalence of marijuana and alcohol consumption was 22% higher in adolescents with a lower SES than in those with a higher SES. Trim and Chassin (2008) found that affluent neighbours may contribute to high level of substance use due to less supervision of children and more exposure to substance using peers.

Counselling Implications

The above research conclusions support the following perspective regarding counseling clients with substance abuse problems. Substance abuse by an individual is a complex behaviour because it is not determined by a single factor. It is determined by the interaction of the agent (drug), host (individual) and the environment (society or culture). Not only the drug taking problem in a person should be a major concern but also the therapeutic modalities to combat the problem must be viewed in its psycho-counselling and socio-culture context.

An excellent resource on how to talk to kids about drugs is: Parents - The Anti-Drug. Parents are encouraged to give clear, no-use messages about smoking, drugs, and alcohol. It is important for kids and teens to understand that the rules and expectations set by parents are based on parental love and concern for their well-being. Parents should also be actively involved and demonstrate interest in their teen's friends and social activities. Spending quality time with teens and setting good examples are essential. Even if problems such as substance abuse already exist in the teen's life, parents and families can still have a positive influence on their teen's behavior. They should consult a counsellor help.

Counselors must first have the ability to develop an open, collaborative relationship with clients wherein clients perceive trust and commitment. Carl Rogers identifies, and research supports, this ability as related to the counselor's skill in conveying, in interaction with clients, unconditional positive regard and empathic understanding (Austin, 1999). Within this relationship, the counselor must provide focus for the process by addressing the client's presenting problems directly and identifying client need for change. Counselors of clients with substance abuse problems often find this process difficult because of the chronic nature of interrelated destructive attitudes and coexisting disorders these clients often bring to counseling. Once problem identification and client need for change are identified, the counselor must be able to articulate and implement counseling intervention strategies perceived by both the counselor and the client as appropriate to the client's need to change.

These process considerations in counseling clients with substance abuse problems hold to be true for specialists in this area and for counselors working in school, rehabilitation, mental health, and social work settings. The counselor emphasis is on the person not the substance abuse problem. Additional

knowledge and skill on the part of the counselor relates to being able to assess the extent and impact of a client's substance abuse problem and the client's need to change. Familiarity with and ability to utilize standardized assessment instruments specific to substance abuse will help the counselor in this assessment process. Familial and social environment assessment also is required to identify the extent of and to utilize the client's support systems. The counselor's ability to identify the needs of the client and the quality of counseling and related treatment intervention strategies obviously linked to his/her assessment and diagnostic skills.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the causative factors of substance abuse are numerous; it is unfortunate that despite years of research and financial investment, drug abuse persists with high incidence. However the search for solution continues because the issue of substance abuse is a serious matter that cannot be ignored.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study and the discussions that followed, it was recommended as follows:

1. There is the need for government to be stricter concerning the policies on importation of hard drugs.
2. Drug users should be rehabilitated after treatment so as to avoid relapse.
3. Advertisement of drugs like alcohol, and smoking of tobacco through the mass media should be banned. Agencies of social change like Nation Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA) should embark on mass public enlightenment campaign to expose the ills, dangers and consequences of substance abuse. Government should be ready to sponsor these programmes, give financial support and see the drug abuser as a sick person who needs help from the government, counsellor, psychiatrist and other social workers.

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